

EBFMC25-OP-74 · Evaluation of the Relationship Between the Leukocyte Glucose Index (LGI) and Disease Stage in Patients with Metabolic Dysfunction Associated Fatty Liver Disease (MASLD)

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver disease (MASLD) is diagnosed with the presence of at least one of the cardiometabolic risk factors such as hepatic steatosis and diabetes mellitus, obesity, hyperlipidemia. It is seen in 20-30% of the world's population and its incidence is increasing. It is expected to be the most common cause of cirrhosis and liver transplantation in 2030. The leukocyte glucose index (LGI), calculated from blood leukocyte and glucose values, has been shown to have predictive values in acute MI, acute CVO and pneumonia in studies (Ishihara et al., 2006; Modan et al., 1975; Seoane et al., 2018; You et al., 2019). In this study, we aimed to show whether LGI predicts the stage of the disease in MASLD.

Material and Method: Between 15.03.2025 and 01.02.2025, patients diagnosed with MASLD at the Ministry of Health and Ordu University Education, Research and were retrospectively screened. 41 patients were included in the study. Age, gender, chronic diseases, hemogram and biochemical parameters of the patients and hepatosteatosis stages from abdominal ultrasound results were recorded. LGI was calculated with the formula: leukocyte (103 μ l) X glucose (mg/dl) /1000. Patients were divided into two groups because they had stage 1 and 2 MASLD. The distribution of data was done with the Kolmogorov Smirnov test. In the comparison of groups, Mann Whitney U test was used for data that were not normally distributed, and Student T test was used for data that were normally distributed. Chi square was used for the comparison of nonparametric data.

Results: The mean age of Stage 1 MASLD was 56.4 \pm 9.6, and the mean age of Stage 1 MASLD was 52 \pm 13.7. 60.7% of the Stage 1 MASLD group was female (n=17), and 31.3% of the Stage 2 MASLD group was female (n=5). When the groups were compared in terms of gender and chronic diseases, no difference was found between the groups. When compared in terms of hemogram and biochemical parameters, higher Fasting plasma glucose (P=0.006), GGT (P=0.005), T. Cholesterol (p=0.04), TG (P=0.008), LGI (P=0.003) and lower HDL (P=0.006) were found in the Stage 2 MASLD group.

Conclusion: Leukocyte glucose index was found to be higher in the Stage 2 MASLD group than in the Stage 1 patient group. LGI index can be used to estimate the MASLD stage in clinical practice.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Leukocyte glucose index, metabolic dysfunction-associated fatty liver disease, MASLD

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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